

Article

Digital Product Passport Design Supporting the Circular Economy Based on the Asset Administration Shell

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Abstract: This paper investigates the design of a digital product passport (DPP) model based on the asset administration shell (AAS) framework to support the circular economy while ensuring cross-industry applicability. In a circular economy, resources are continuously reused, fostering more sustainable manufacturing. The European Commission's initiatives target this issue, with the DPP playing a critical role in sharing product sustainability information, such as product composition and repairability, throughout its lifecycle. However, a widely applicable DPP approach has yet to be established. This study consolidates existing standards, and scientific literature to develop a data model that aligns with circular economy principles. Using the AAS framework initially developed by the Plattform Industrie 4.0, we mapped the data requirements to submodel templates and addressed gaps in the data needed for real-life implementation. The results demonstrate that the proposed DPP data model is specific enough for practical use cases, such as the upcoming EU battery passport, while remaining flexible enough for application across various industries. The AAS framework's adaptability and comprehensive data exchange capabilities make it a suitable foundation for developing DPPs that support the transition to a circular economy.

Keywords: circular economy; digital product passport; asset administration shell; Industry 4.0; sustainable manufacturing

Academic Editors: Filippo Marciano, Giuseppe Tomasoni and Paola Cocca

Received: 15 November 2024

Revised: 20 January 2025

Accepted: 21 January 2025

Published: 24 January 2025

Citation: Kühn, M.; Baumann, M.; Volz, F.; Stojanovic, L. Digital Product Passport Design Supporting the Circular Economy Based on the Asset Administration Shell. *Sustainability* **2025**, *17*, 969. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su17030969>

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1. Introduction

The EU aims to move from a linear economy to a circular economy to decouple economic growth from resource use, as half of total greenhouse gas emissions and more than 90% of biodiversity loss come from resource extraction and processing [1]. To that end, the EU issued the Circular Economy Action Plan (CEAP) [1] which is one of the main building blocks of the European Green Deal [2]. By redesigning production and consumption processes, the circular economy seeks to minimize waste, reduce resource consumption, and close material loops through activities such as reuse, recycling, and remanufacturing. The 9R strategy framework, a key component of CE, provides a structured approach for these activities, ranging from more preferable R-strategies such as “Refuse” and “Reduce” to less preferable ones like “Recycle” and “Recover”. Through these R-strategies, the circular economy promotes sustainable manufacturing.

Sustainable manufacturing is a concept that has been analyzed from different viewpoints depending on its purpose, dimensions, and application [3]. The most widely accepted dimensions of sustainable manufacturing are the environment, economy, and social dimensions [4]. Sustainable manufacturing concerns the entire product lifecycle [5]. Therefore,

sustainable manufacturing requires solutions that themselves address the entire product lifecycle such as the circular economy. The benefits of a circular economy can be mapped to the three dimensions of sustainable manufacturing. In addition to environmental aspects such as reduced waste, a circular economy offers economic and social benefits by extending product lifecycles, fostering innovation, and creating new job opportunities. In the manufacturing domain, a circular economy can have positive financial impacts by lowering the amount of raw material required for component manufacturers [6]. Through rebuying their used components, they can also lower production costs and make their supply chain more robust. Recyclers benefit from the provision of exhaustive information on product usage and composition, so they can work more efficiently. Still, there are no data models that are modeled explicitly to support R-strategies while building upon existing standards and being applicable across industries [7]. This work therefore focuses on the research question: How can a digital product passport model based on the asset administration shell be designed to support the circular economy while ensuring cross-industry applicability?

The 9R-strategy framework takes the entire product lifecycle into account [8]. In a circular economy, the product lifecycle can be described as a loop. According to [9], this loop begins in the resource extraction phase and continues with the manufacturing and usage phase. The loop is connected between the end-of-life phase and the manufacturing phase. For each lifecycle phase, there is a set of relevant R-strategies that can help to fulfill a specific function in a circular economy. As described in [9], there are three major functions within a circular economy: narrowing the loop, slowing the loop down and closing the loop. “Narrowing the loop” refers to smarter product design, “slowing the loop” refers to extending the lifespan of products and their parts and “closing the loop” refers to the useful application of materials at the end of life. Even though covering all R-strategies is necessary for an effective circular economy, we decided to limit the scope of this article to “slowing the loop”, because it is closely linked to sustainable manufacturing. The R-strategy framework is displayed in Figure 1. In summary, we apply the R-strategy framework as the main principle of the circular economy in our study, while focusing on the R-strategies of remanufacturing, refurbishing, repair, and reuse. According to [8], these are defined as follows:

- R3: Reuse by another consumer of the discarded product which is still in good condition and fulfills the original function.
- R4: Repair and maintenance of the defective product so it can be used with its original function.
- R5: Refurbishment of an old product to bring it up to date.
- R6: Remanufacturing a defective product by using parts of discarded products in a new product with the same function.

Figure 1. Circular thinking based on [10].

A circular economy heavily relies on a solid informational foundation to find the most effective R-strategy and to realize that R-strategy for a product. As described above, data from across the entire lifecycle and from all stakeholders in the value chain have to be taken into account. To foster the data exchange of products, the European commission issued the concept of a digital product passport (DPP) that will be mandatory for certain types of products by 2026, such as batteries [1]. A DPP is an essential tool for enabling the holistic and comprehensive collection of information about a product for different actors such as consumers and waste management companies [11]. A DPP poses technical challenges with regard to requirements like interoperability and data sovereignty. So far, there is no technical standard for DPPs [12] but the asset administration shell (AAS) is a promising candidate [13]. The AAS is a central component of the German government's "Plattform Industrie 4.0" initiative and is designed to create digital representation of business assets. It serves as a standardized framework for collecting and exchanging data throughout the lifecycle of an asset, supporting various stakeholders in accessing up-to-date and synchronized information. There are three different types of AAS [14]. AAS Type 1 is a static file format that is used for interoperable data exchange. AAS Type 2 plays a crucial role by enabling the integration of standardized APIs, which ensures that all stakeholders can access and update relevant data seamlessly. This capability is essential for implementing the circular economy, as it ensures that critical information—such as product composition, maintenance history, and recycling potential—remains accessible and accurate throughout the product's lifecycle. AAS Type 3 is a concept with the goal to allow assets to communicate autonomously and negotiate contracts. The informational content of an AAS is structured in submodels. Each submodel is a collection of data and services related to a specific aspect of the asset. Submodels consist of properties that define specific attributes or parameters of the asset. Operations can be defined within submodels to perform certain actions or processes relevant to the asset. Submodels that are standardized by the Industrial Digital Twin Association (IDTA) are called submodel templates. By utilizing these templates for different kinds of assets, interoperability is established. At the time of writing this document there are 26 published IDTA submodel templates [15]. These model information such as functional safety, nameplate and carbon footprint. These templates are one of the advantages to use the AAS to define DPPs for different products. However, there are no submodel templates specifically designed to support the circular economy currently in development.

DPP State of the Art

Digital product passports (DPPs) have gained increasing attention as a key enabler for promoting transparency and sustainability in the circular economy. By providing detailed information about a product's lifecycle, including its environmental impact and recyclability, DPPs facilitate informed decision-making for both businesses and consumers. This has led to the development of various DPP models. The CIRPASS project collected 98 different DPP efforts by developing a detailed characterization framework to systematically classify initiatives across dimensions such as actors, technical design, and data [7]. Some of these DPP efforts are based on the AAS framework, while others have been designed specifically for circular economy applications without relying on AAS. The choice of framework and data model plays a critical role in determining the flexibility, scalability, and cross-industry applicability of the DPP.

Examples of the investigated DPPs in the CIRPASS project include the DPP4.0 and PCDS. The DPP4.0 is described as an industry-ready way of collecting and providing product information in a human- and machine-readable format for different parties, such as companies, authorities, and users [16]. The ZVEI-Show-Case PCF@Control Cabinet

demonstrates how DPP4.0 can be used to calculate the product carbon footprint (PCF) of an integrated system that contains a variety of products supplied by different manufacturers [17]. Information about the data model of the DPP4.0 can be inferred from the ZVEI Show-Case. The DPP4.0 for version 2.0 of the ZVEI Show-Case is based on currently published submodel templates. However, the DPP4.0 does not explicitly support the circular economy through required data or key performance indicators (KPIs). Regarding DPPs that are explicitly modeled for the circular economy without using the AAS standard, the product circularity data sheet (PCDS) should be mentioned. In [18], the authors proposed the PCDS with the aim of enabling the exchange of standardized data across the entire supply cycle and thus supporting DPP systems. The PCDS was defined to provide basic product circularity data, improve the efficiency of circularity data exchange, and ensure improved product circularity performance. One of the design principles of the PCDS is to provide standardized information for others to perform circularity evaluations. This was carried out in the form of the PCDS template, which is divided into five sections, each of which contains parameters that can only be answered with yes or no. This is intended to help resolve the conflict between confidentiality and transparency. Our proposal is also based on aspects of the circular economy while building upon the AAS standard. In our model, it is not necessary to limit the values of the parameters to “true” or “false” as technical means (e.g., data space usage policies) should be used to control the access and usage of the data.

The growing number of research publications shows a strong academic and practical interest in the use of AAS to create resilient and effective DPPs. However, analysis of the current research landscape in this area has shown that it is more about the applicability of AASs than about contributing to the AAS standard itself to make it more suitable for DPPs. In [11], the authors explored the role of the DPP for different stakeholders and analyzed which data could be collected and made available to which stakeholders, and how. Although at the time of writing the paper AASs were primarily used for production assets, the authors discussed the potential of AASs for modeling DPPs, as an AAS covers the entire life cycle of an asset. They found the AAS-based approach particularly suitable for the required “continuous multidirectional feeding of product-specific (in contrast to model-specific) information”. In addition to modeling DPPs, the authors argue that the AASs could also be used as a basis for multidirectional data exchange regarding single products, as the AAS standard also provides an API. However, this work is only at the conceptual level as it discusses issues relevant to the realization of DPPs and does not provide a solution for the realization of DPPs. In this paper, we follow the proposed approach of using AASs for DPPs but make it much more concrete. The contributions are twofold. First, we make a proposal for the AAS submodel templates required to model circularity-relevant aspects. Second, we evaluate the proposed approach by demonstrating its applicability in a practical case study for the battery passport.

In [19], the authors highlight how KPIs help in designing products for sustainability. They suggest using digital twins as a solution for keeping the KPIs up to date. In this work, we build upon this approach by using the AAS as a standard for digital twins as well as circularity KPIs derived from standards and norms. By consistently focusing on standards, we make it easy to adopt the DPP design presented here.

Starting from the interoperability and privacy requirements for digital representations of products/assets, AASs were used in [20] to realize a multi-stakeholder perspective on DPPs. The use of AASs made it possible to consider not only the manufacturing phase of a product but also all phases in the product lifecycle including the later life cycle phases. The authors presented their cloud-based system that allows multiple stakeholders to create their own AASs. They proposed that a DPP should be stored centrally in the cloud and

that all relevant stakeholders should be able to access it (to read or write data) based on role-based access control. Although it is not clear if and how role-based access control could currently be realized with AAS, as the security part of the standardization is still under development, the authors focused mainly on the explanatory functionality of their system and less on the modeling approach. However, they confirmed that there is a need for standardized submodel templates that will contribute to even greater interoperability, but this aspect will be the subject of their future research. The main difference in our approach is that we consider the AAS metamodel and the existing AAS submodel templates to be insufficient for the circular economy use case and therefore propose how these aspects could be modelled within AAS. On the system side, instead of a cloud-based solution for information exchange, we propose building on the IDS data spaces. The reason for this is that the implementation of the data space building blocks is already available, including the module for the integration between an AAS and a connector, and that the data exchange could take place at the level of any AAS entity.

In [21], the authors presented how a DPP concept could be realized based on the AAS and how it might be used to calculate the carbon footprint. Since the DPP requires an infrastructure for data exchange between different stakeholders, where not everyone has access to all information, the authors proposed a solution based on the Gaia-X project to ensure data sovereignty and security. Regarding AAS modelling, the authors used standardized AAS submodel templates such as the “Contact information” submodel template, which contains all relevant information for the interoperable provision of contact information. Regarding circularity, the product’s carbon footprint submodel template was used to represent the carbon footprint of the production or transportation steps inside an AAS. Although the approach was validated in a use case of sorting electronic devices to support recycling with the DPP, it remains unclear how the aspects related to recycling were modeled by using AASs. The authors also proposed using existing standards, such as DIN 77005 part 2 [22], for modelling product lifecycle. However, there is neither an existing AAS submodel nor did the authors propose one for this purpose. Additionally, the authors discovered the need to model lifecycle assessment based on DIN 91474 [23] in the form of an AAS submodel template [24]. There is a gap between theoretical DPP concepts and DPPs that can be readily used for interoperable data exchange across company borders. The main contribution of our paper is to bridge this gap by modeling concrete submodel templates based on existing standards with the goal of supporting the realization of R-strategies. The modeling is based on the approach proposed in [21] and follows two opposing guidelines: The submodel templates should be specific enough to be applicable in real-world scenarios while being generic enough to be suitable for a wide range of products. Through an analysis of existing standards and a case study on batteries, we demonstrate how the AAS can be leveraged to create a comprehensive and adaptable DPP model that supports the circular economy.

2. Materials and Methods

This section describes the methodology applied to collect data requirements for a DPP that supports the circular economy’s R-strategies, specifically remanufacturing, refurbishing, repair, and reuse. This process began with a review of existing standards that specify information needed by different stakeholder groups to implement these R-strategies effectively, which is essential due to the known barriers that a lack of information along the value chain can pose. Standards, by defining stakeholder-specific information needs, provide a foundational framework for enabling R-strategies on a “need-to-know” basis. However, we found the investigated standards to be lacking in specific requirements related to product usage data. Therefore, we complemented the data requirements from the standards with additional requirements from the literature, particularly drawing from two

key studies. In [25], the authors developed a robust methodology by combining scientific and grey literature reviews with practical insights from stakeholders via a questionnaire filled out by ten manufacturers and nine end-of-life actors. Their approach provided a broad, though somewhat generalized, list of data requirements for DPPs. The authors of [26], on the other hand, focused on DPPs within the circular economy and identified gaps in lifecycle traceability, underscoring the need for a standardized framework. This literature-based approach allowed us to capture a more comprehensive set of requirements, particularly those absent in current standards, enabling a more holistic foundation for the DPP's role in supporting R-strategies.

2.1. Data Requirements from Standards

The relevant standards for our DPP design are derived from a broad-based research of the standardization landscape conducted by DIN, DKE and VDI in relation to the circular economy as part of the project “standardization roadmap circular economy” [27]. It provides a comprehensive overview of existing standards for topics derived from the EU Commission’s Circular Economy Action Plan such as electrotechnology, batteries and textiles among others. Furthermore, they investigated existing standards regarding cross-cutting topics. The digital product passport is identified as one of these cross-cutting topics. We focused on the standards related to the main topic electrotechnology and the cross-cutting topic of the DPP and found “DIN EN 45554—General methods for the assessment of the ability to repair, reuse and upgrade energy related products” [28] and “DIN SPEC 91472—Remanufacturing (Reman)—Quality classification for circular processes” [23] to be of highest relevance for our endeavor. First, because they are directly related to R-strategies and cover all four R-strategies that we focus on in this publication. Secondly, because they meet our central goal of being specific enough to be applicable to real-life use cases while being generic enough to be applicable to a wide range of products from the manufacturing domain.

DIN EN 45554 details general methods for the assessment of the ability to repair, reuse and upgrade energy-related products. Mapping the textual requirements of the assessments as specified in this document into entities of a standardized data model for a DPP therefore supports the realization of R-strategies R3 to R5. This standard is especially useful to support the modelling of the DPP because it is approved by European standardization organizations already. The information requirements detailed in DIN EN 45554 are separated into ten categories:

1. **Disassembly depth:** This is the number of steps required to remove a part of a product, without damaging the product. This property is essential to describe the effort required to replace parts. For details on the calculation of the disassembly depth, see [28].
2. **Fasteners and connectors:** The number and visibility of fasteners and connectors relates to the time needed to repair or upgrade a product. It is important to state if fasteners are reusable, removable or neither.
3. **Tools:** To repair or upgrade a product effectively, it is necessary that the required tools are specified.
4. **Working environment:** Similarly, some products may require specialized working environments like workshops, to be repaired or upgraded effectively.
5. **Skill level:** Depending on the categories mentioned above, some repair or upgrade operations can only be feasible for persons with a certain skill level. Skill levels can range from layman to authorized experts.
6. **Diagnostic support and interfaces:** Intuitive interfaces for the identification of a problem or fault can aid repair, reuse, and refurbishment.

7. Availability of spare parts: The availability of spare parts should be stated with respect to the respective target group (publicly available, available for authorized service providers) and the time period.
8. Type and availability of information: For this category, the comprehensiveness as well as the availability to specific target groups is required.
9. Return options: For a product owner to assess the possibility of returning a product for reuse, refurbishment or repair, the return options should be specified.
10. Data management: It is important that for a product to be reused the ownership can be transferred without the transfer of any personal or otherwise sensitive data. Therefore, data management methods should be specified.

For each of these categories, a product can fall into one of several classes, e.g., from “A” to “D”, depending on how much they hinder the ability of a product to be repaired, reused and/or upgraded. For example, if for the repair of a specific product only tools are required that are delivered with the product itself, the product can be classified as “A” within the “Tools” category. If, however, the product requires proprietary tools to be repaired that are only available to the manufacturer, it can be classified as “D” within the “Tools” category. For details on the different classes for each category, see [28]. This classification system allows for a scoring system that summarizes the ability of a product to be repaired, reused and/or upgraded. The score can be calculated by replacing the letters for the classes with numeric values where higher values refer to greater ability of the product to be repaired, reused and/or refurbished. In combination with weights for each category, the repairability, reusability and/or upgradeability can be expressed in a single value. The standard does not specify any of the numerical values or weights but leaves the attribution up to the user of the standard. Consequently, the scoring is not standardized and will depend on the specific application. Based on this standard, we propose that a data model that supports the repair, refurbishment and reuse of a product is required to specify the necessary information for the ten categories. This includes the textual information as well as the classification of this information.

DIN SPEC 91472 is concerned with remanufacturing and quality classification for circular processes. Mapping the information for the classification as specified in this document into a standardized data model for a DPP aids the realization of R-strategy R6.

A major result of this standard is the definition of two key indicators that measure the circularity of manufactured products, namely, the product composition circularity indicator (PCI) and the end of use circularity indicator (ECI). The PCI is an indicator used to quantify the circularity of the product composition of remanufactured products and other circular products. It takes values between 0 and 1, where the value 0 describes a product that is exclusively composed out of original parts and the value 1 describes a product that is composed exclusively out of directly reused parts. For calculation purposes components are differentiated as new part, restored part, reused part and direct reuse parts. Each of these parts can be attributed to a different value-retention process factor where direct reuse parts have the highest whereas new parts have the lowest value-retention process factor. The ECI is an indicator used to quantify the circularity of the actual destination of remanufactured products and other circular products after a use phase. It takes values between 0 and 1. It takes the value 0 if the product is destined for landfill or thermal recovery and the value 1 if the product will be perfectly reused without material losses and new material requirements. To calculate these indicators, information about the amount and mass of each component of a product is required. Additionally, the PCI requires information about the origin of the components. Were they manufactured specifically for that product (new part) or are they second life components? Depending on how much effort was required to use the second life component (refurbish, reuse with minor adjustments

or direct reuse), the component is considered differently. Similarly, the ECI depends on the destination of the component. Is it destined for landfill after the end of life of the product? Or can it be used within a remanufactured product with different degrees of effort like the ones mentioned above? Since the origin and destination of a component can in practice be different from the specified origin/destination, the authors state that it is important to state quotas based on empirical findings to calculate PCI and ECI values that describe the reality more accurately. Additionally, return options must be specified for each product since this has major implications on the actual return rates of components. For example, a manufacturer could specify an address where specific parts can be handed in for remanufacturing. The ECI and PCI are useful for measuring the actual circularity of products with respect to remanufacturing and can to this end serve as KPIs. Based on this standard, we propose that a data model that supports remanufacturing is required to specify the necessary information to calculate the PCI/ECI and information about the return options.

From this investigation, we can derive a lack of usage data in the standards above for the effective realization of R-strategies. Traditionally, the main objectives of standards were to ensure safety, functionality, and compatibility of products. To support a circular economy, standards have to focus more on resource conservation, product-life extension, value and quality preservation, and waste prevention [27]. These goals depend much more on product usage. The significance of usage data is also emphasized in [27]: “[...] in addition to comprehensive and consistent product information, usage history is particularly relevant for secondary users. [...] The use of a digital product passport can facilitate the update of the usage history”. Therefore, we propose data requirements stemming from the usage of products that complement the requirements from the technical standards.

2.2. Data Requirements from the Literature

In [25], the authors collected requirements for the DPP from various perspectives in order to support the circular economy. The requirements were identified on the basis of the literature research, the results of the questionnaire and discussions with experts. The information requirements are classified into data related to manufacturing, usage, life cycle and end-of-life data. For usage data, the authors specify that changes to any parts that have been replaced or repaired should be documented. Furthermore, damage to components should be recorded. Manufacturing data should include comprehensive details about the product’s composition, material properties, technical data like joining techniques, and any potential hazards. End-of-life data emphasize collection, sorting, recycling methods, and output streams, providing feedback that can support product design for circularity. Lifecycle data include sales volumes for resource and waste planning, usage guidelines to minimize environmental risks. While the paper provides an excellent analysis of the data that could be relevant, it does not provide a formal specification or model of how these data could be represented, which is the main contribution of our paper. Additionally, according to the authors, the contribution of [25] is to be understood as a first proposal for DPP requirements. In this paper, we extend them to include requirements from a circular economy perspective and try to keep them general enough to be applicable to any type of product.

The data requirements identified by [26] are organized into seven data categories to comprehensively cover a product’s lifecycle. Material data include detailed information on materials used, such as type, specifications, and quantity, acting as a potential bill of materials for later recycling efforts. Environmental data focus on tracking the environmental footprint, covering both the impacts of materials and the manufacturing process to allow lifecycle monitoring. Manufacturing data capture all production details, including sensor

data and machine performance, for improved traceability and process optimization. Value network data store information generated across the product's value chain, such as logistics and tracking data, to enhance visibility from manufacturing through to the end user. Maintenance data record all information about upkeep and repairs performed once the product is in use, while circularity data are critical for tracking reuse, recycling, and other circular actions taken after the product's initial life, providing insights on the effectiveness of circularity strategies and facilitating better lifecycle management. Lastly, end-user data house information for product use by the owner, such as usage instructions and maintenance guidelines, to ensure users have the necessary knowledge for sustainable product use. Our contribution expands on [26] by developing a more industry-specific framework for DPPs that adapts to different product types and builds upon existing standards to ease implementation. This refinement addresses key integration and adoption barriers, paving the way for DPPs to enhance transparency and sustainability across manufacturing and circular economies.

3. Results

We propose that a DPP should be modeled using an AAS. This allows for seamless integration of DPP data with existing product-specific data and avoids data redundancy. In this way, the data model is based on a standardized meta model and API. Furthermore, the AAS API allows the DPP to store dynamic data. In this way, the AAS provides a data sharing ecosystem that fulfills many of the requirements regarding successful collaboration and identification mentioned in the literature. In this section, we present AAS submodels that fulfill the data requirements listed above. For modeling within the framework of submodels, it makes sense to determine whether there are already submodel templates that cover these data. The analysis of the submodel templates also reveals gaps that are not yet covered and should be developed and standardized by new submodel templates for the circular economy.

Figure 2 shows a list of submodel templates that we suggest for modeling a DPP supporting the circular economy. This is not to be understood as an exhaustive list since there can be additional data requirements depending on the use case. However, this is a solid foundation for making informed decisions about possible R-strategies for a wide range of different products. From this list, the submodel templates "Nameplate", "Technical Data", "Predictive Maintenance", "Carbon Footprint", "Hierarchical Structures" and "Spare Parts And Consumables" are already published by the industrial digital twin association (IDTA) or are in the process of being published. The submodel templates "Circularity Assessment", "Return Options" and "Usage Data" are our contribution in order to fulfill the data requirements detailed above and close information gaps regarding the circular economy. In the following, we explain these submodels one by one.

SM	<T> "Nameplate" [https://admin-shell.io/idta/Nameplate/Template/2/0/Submodel]
SM	<T> "TechnicalData" [https://admin-shell.io/ZVEI/TechnicalData/Submodel/1/2]
SM	<T> "PredictiveMaintenance" [https://admin-shell.io/idta/PredictiveMaintenance/Template/0/9/Submodel]
SM	<T> "CarbonFootprint" [https://admin-shell.io/idta/CarbonFootprint/CarbonFootprint/0/9]
SM	<T> "HierarchicalStructures" [https://admin-shell.io/idta/HierarchicalStructures/Template/1/0/Submodel]
SM	<T> "SparePartsAndConsumables" [https://admin-shell.io/idta/SparePartsAndConsumablesList/Template/0/1/Submodel]
SM	<T> "CircularityAssessment" [https://iosb.fraunhofer.de/aas/CircularityAssessment/Template/0/9/Submodel]
SM	<T> "ReturnOptions" [https://iosb.fraunhofer.de/aas/ReturnOptions/Template/0/9/Submodel]
SM	<T> "UsageData" [https://iosb.fraunhofer.de/aas/OperationalData/Template/0/9/Submodel]

Figure 2. List of submodels for a DPP supporting the circular economy as displayed by the Eclipse AASX Package explorer [29].

3.1. Existing Submodel Templates

The submodel template's Nameplate standardizes nameplate information to comply with relevant regulations, overcoming the limitations of traditional labeling. It enables global access to asset information, providing functions such as verifying asset identity and ensuring compliance with safety standards [30]. The digital Nameplate submodel is indispensable for a wide range of use cases where the interoperable identification of assets across company borders is required. Since, in a circular economy, numerous stakeholders have to cooperate to prolong the lifespan of assets, it is self-evident to include this submodel template within a DPP for a circular economy.

The Technical Data submodel template enables the interoperable provision of asset-related technical data within the AAS [31]. It facilitates clear communication by standardizing the structure of technical data using dictionaries such as ECLASS and IEC CDD, making information accessible in multiple languages. This template provides key asset data needed by manufacturers, system integrators, and operators to evaluate and use equipment effectively. Structured into sections, the template includes general equipment information for initial identification, product classification to establish market relevance, and detailed technical properties, such as dimensions, material composition and production characteristics. Additional context, such as manufacturer statements or validity dates, enhances the technical data provided, ensuring all relevant information about the asset is readily available for engineering, procurement, and operational needs.

The Predictive Maintenance submodel template is designed to standardize the provision of metadata and information from sub-systems within highly automated production lines, crucial for predictive maintenance (PM) solutions [32]. A high level overview is displayed in Figure 3. It facilitates the integration of these sub-systems into PM systems, enabling targeted data evaluation to reduce unplanned machine downtimes by predicting component failures and providing maintenance-relevant information. The submodel addresses key aspects of predictive maintenance, including condition monitoring, fault diagnosis, and remaining useful life (RUL) prediction, as defined by the DIN EN IEC 63270 standard [33]. It is applicable to production environments with multiple sub-systems focusing on the early detection of wear, faults, and other issues to minimize downtime. The submodel provides semantic descriptions of the sub-systems' condition indicators, fault modes, and RUL. It includes time-based properties tied to wear-relevant units like operation cycles or distances, fault diagnosis independent of RUL prediction, and tracks maintenance events [32]. The condition indicators and maintenance events are valuable information describing the usage history of a product. Using these data greatly improves decision making regarding the appropriate R-strategy for a product. The Condition Monitoring data structure contains all application-specific time series data that are recorded during use for various operating parameters. These could be, for example, operating conditions such as temperature or humidity, but also the process parameters of a product over time, such as power consumption or compressed air consumption, as well as other process parameters that allow conclusions to be drawn about the load and thus the wear. In the case of a plastic injection molding machine, for example, this could be the injection pressure or the tool temperature; in the case of a washing machine, this could be vibrations or increased motor power. In general, an increase or deviation in these parameters from the standard values can indicate wear or other problems. This means that such operating parameters should be monitored regularly in order to detect signs of wear at an early stage and initiate maintenance measures. The remaining useful life prediction for sub-systems can be used to apply R-strategies effectively and enable business models to build upon buying back used machines and components. Filling in the entire Predictive Maintenance submodel template might be too demanding or not applicable to simpler products. However, the

submodel element collections “Remaining Useful Life Prediction” and “Last Maintenance Relevant Events” collect information about the current state and the maintenance history of the product which are highly relevant for finding the appropriate R-strategy.

Figure 3. High level overview of the Predictive Maintenance submodel template as displayed by the Eclipse AASX Package Explorer [29].

The Carbon Footprint submodel template enables efficient exchange of a product’s carbon footprint (PCF) across value chain partners, including manufacturers, users, and logistics partners [34]. Aimed at promoting interoperability, this template supports documentation, assessment, and optimization of a product’s environmental impacts. It aligns with larger sustainability initiatives, though it does not replace official certification. The submodel supports diverse use cases and allows multiple PCF values by accommodating various calculation methods, scopes, and standards (e.g., ISO 14044, ISO 14067, Greenhouse Gas Protocol [24,35,36]). Each method or standard is represented through distinct submodel element collections.

The submodel template “Hierarchical Structures” aims to standardize the representation of hierarchical structures within industrial equipment in an interoperable manner [37]. It facilitates the identification and organization of assets, by providing a structured framework that links these assets to their corresponding AAS. It is intended to provide a description of the internal structure of an asset which is not possible to do using the AAS itself because nesting of AAS and submodels is forbidden by the metamodel. The appropriate R-strategy for an asset greatly depends on the state of the components within the asset, like the remaining useful life. Being able to identify the respective components of an asset automatically requires the use of the hierarchical structures submodel template.

The Spare Parts and Consumables List submodel template is a newly submitted proposal. Therefore, no specific information can be given about the structure and information content of this submodel. In any case, a submodel that contains information about spare parts and consumables is highly relevant for a DPP supporting the circular economy as it greatly facilitates information exchange regarding the replacement of broken components. In combination with the hierarchical structures, submodel template replacement parts can be identified quickly.

3.2. Circularity Assessment Submodel

To close the informational gap with respect to the effective realization of R-strategies, we created three additional submodels: the Circularity Assessment submodel, the Return Options submodel and the Usage Data submodel. The Circularity Assessment submodel template (Figure 4) serves to provide indicators that state the circularity of a product similar to how the product carbon footprint submodel template describes the environmental friendliness of a product. These indicators are the PCI and ECI mentioned above. It also includes the repairability score. However, we refer to it as the circularity design score since it is not only relevant for repair but also for reuse, refurbish and remanufacture. The information used for calculating the circularity design score, as specified in DIN EN 45554, is the same for each product type and is closely related to the design for circularity. These indicators can act as KPIs to support decision making regarding the design for circularity,

as well as being valuable information for regulators. For example, a change in product design that allows for repair with more accessible tools could lead to a better ECI for specific products.

Figure 4. Overview of the Circularity assessment submodel as displayed by the Eclipse AASX Package explorer [29].

The submodel contains the information from which the circularity indicators are derived. For the calculation of the Circularity Design score, the information is provided in the Circularity Design submodel element collection. The properties contained here correspond to the information requirements detailed in Section 2. Each property may be valuable for end customers on its own. For example, they can use the information to compare products of different manufacturers with respect to the skill level one needs to repair the product.

To make the calculation of the PCI and ECI from the DPP model possible, we had to keep two possible cases in mind. First, it might be the case that the product requiring a DPP is composed out of multiple components, for example, a washing machine that is composed out of a drum, motor, pump, etc. It cannot be assumed that there exists a DPP for each of these components. Therefore, there is a submodel element list that stores circularity information about the components. This information is mandatory to calculate the PCI and the ECI of the product and includes “Amount”, “Mass”, “Origin” and “Destination” as specified in the information requirements in Section 2. If there is another AAS containing information about one or several components, it can be linked via the submodel template “Hierarchical Structures”. It is important to note that it is not necessary to have the entire bill of materials for a product to calculate the ECI and PCI. One hierarchy level downwards should generally suffice. In the case of the washing machine, the motor itself is composed

out of several components, but to calculate the PCI of the washing machine, it is sufficient to know the origin and mass of the motor itself. It is not necessary to know the origin and mass of the rotor, windings, and connection terminals inside the motor. Nevertheless, a PCI for the motor of the washing machine could have already been calculated. In that case, the PCI of the motor can be used for the calculation of the PCI of the washing machine, leading to a more nuanced description of the washing machine. Second, it might be the case that the product requiring a DPP is itself a component of another product. For example, a battery that is part of a car. Therefore, the “origin”, “destination” and “mass” properties are included for the product itself. This is not only helpful in calculating the ECI and PCI but also to track the usage history of a product. Furthermore, the mass of the product can be used to make sure that there is no component circularity information missing. In the case of a difference between the product mass and the aggregated component mass, the difference has to be assumed as origin “new part” and destination “landfill”.

It is important to note that using the mass of components as weights in the calculation of the ECI and PCI of products can lead to undesired biases towards heavy components. For example, a battery pack casing is a relatively heavy component usually made of aluminum or steel, while the battery management system is a light component that contains lots of precious materials. It is debatable whether KPIs describing the circularity of a battery should depend more on the casing than on the battery management system. Instead of the weight, the financial value of each component could therefore be used as weights for the calculation of the PCI and ECI. It might be more beneficial if the financial value of products within a circular economy is maximized instead of maximizing for the mass of products within a circular economy. This poses practical difficulties, however, since the financial value of components is subject to change and might be information that stakeholders want to keep confidential. Since the standard specified to use the mass as weights, we included them in the submodel template despite the aforementioned bias.

3.3. Return Options Submodel

The submodel “Return Options” (Figure 5) serves to provide comprehensive information regarding the available R-strategy service providers for a product, e.g., a repair service provider or a used-market vendor. It is supposed to be simplistic to make the process of finding suitable R-strategy providers as straightforward as possible. This can greatly facilitate the practical application of R-strategies by providing essential information. The submodel includes a list of submodel element collections that are made up of the contact information template and a property that specifies what kind of R-strategies the contact can provide. Multiple return types per contact are possible.

Figure 5. Overview of the return options submodel template as displayed by the Eclipse AASX Package explorer [29].

3.4. Usage Data Submodel

We designed this submodel to fill the gaps regarding the information on product usage that is not already included in the Predictive Maintenance submodel template. A major aim of the DPP model is to allow for more sustainable manufacturing. Therefore,

specific care was taken that the model can be applied to support the remanufacturing, refurbishment, repair and reuse of production machines. These machines manufacture products and can be viewed as products themselves. The operational data requirements from the machinery sector are transferable to many other products whose wear depends on use and the maintenance and repair measures carried out. Products that are comparable to machines in terms of their wear behavior usually have mechanical or moving components that wear out due to friction, stress, or other physical influences. Examples of this could be cars, motorcycles, bicycles, batteries, washing machines, dishwashers, vacuum cleaners, fitness equipment, etc.

We are aware that not all the data can be applied to every product, so the data fields are not mandatory. However, the model is designed in a way that it can be applied to a wide range of products apart from production machines.

The Usage Data submodel data are divided into the following categories (Figure 6):

- Operating times;
- Performance data;
- Energy consumption data.

Figure 6. Overview of the usage Data submodel template as displayed by the Eclipse AASX Package explorer [29].

Each of these data categories provides valuable information that helps to evaluate the effects of previous use, including signs of wear and tear, to draw conclusions about possible future uses. The structure of Operating Times is based on the VDMA 66412-1 standard sheet Manufacturing Execution Systems Key Performance Indicators [38]. This has given rise to the international standard ISO/DIS 22400-2 Automation systems and integration—Key performance indicators (KPIs) for manufacturing operations management—Part 2: Definition and descriptions [39]. This standard defines the most important time elements that are included in various KPI calculations. The times of the Operating Times submodel are also taken from this specification:

- **Calendar days:**
The total number of days in the period under consideration, regardless of whether the product is in use or not. This is used in the submodel to define the total usage time of a product.
- **Busy time:**
The period of time during which a machine or plant is productive, including production time and setup time, but excluding planned and unplanned downtime. It includes interruptions caused by faults that occur during processing and prolong it.
- **Production time:**
The actual time during which a machine or system is used for production, excluding set-up times, maintenance times and downtimes. It includes only the value-adding functions. It includes time losses depending on speed and quality issues.
- **Maintenance time:**
The amount of time spent on planned or unplanned maintenance.
- **Down time:**
The amount of time a product is unavailable due to unplanned events, such as breakdowns or defects.

These data are essential for the circular economy as they provide insights into product use. Regarding sustainable manufacturing, companies can optimize the efficiency of their production processes, better plan maintenance intervals and minimize downtime by analyzing these times. This helps to extend the service life of machines and reduce resource consumption.

Performance Data are very important for classifying the recycling, reuse or remanufacturing of a product. They enable an accurate assessment of the current condition and remaining life of a product. They help to determine the economic viability of recycling, reuse or remanufacturing by evaluating costs and benefits. They also ensure that only functional and high-quality components are reused or refurbished. Some of the following data points are specific to assets in the manufacturing domain. These performance data also ensure that only safe and reliable components are returned to the cycle.

In the submodel, the performance data include key performance indicators such as

- **Load cycles:**
The number of complete load cycles an asset undergoes during its operation. A load cycle typically comprises a phase of loading and a phase of unloading. This key figure is important for evaluating the fatigue and wear of materials and components.
- **Production rate:**
The quantity of products produced in a given unit of time. It is often measured in units per hour or units per shift. This key figure helps to evaluate the efficiency and productivity of a production process.
- **Throughput:**
The total quantity of material or products that flows through a system or process within a certain period of time. This metric is often measured in units per hour and indicates how much output a system delivers in practice.
- **Yield:**
The percentage of units produced that meet quality requirements and can be sold or further processed as finished products. This metric is calculated as $(\text{number of units accepted} / \text{total number of units produced}) \times 100$ and gives an indication of the efficiency and quality of the production process.

By analyzing performance data, the best possible decision can be made that maximizes both economic and environmental benefits.

Energy Consumption provides information to make informed decisions about the continued use or recycling of a product, taking into account economic, environmental and regulatory aspects. For example, high energy consumption can be an indicator of the condition of a product. An increase in energy consumption can indicate wear and tear or inefficiencies. A product with high energy consumption could be uneconomical and more suitable for recycling, while an efficient product could be more suitable for reuse or refactoring. In addition, regulatory requirements can define rules and standards regarding energy efficiency and CO₂ emissions. Energy consumption data are essential to ensure that products meet these requirements and can influence the decision to reuse, refactor or recycle. The following energy consumption data are provided in the submodel:

- Energy consumption (power):
Indicates the actual energy consumption over a specified period of time in kilowatt hours (kWh).
- Compressed air:
The amount of compressed air consumed during a specified time period. Compressed air is often measured in liters per minute (L/min).
- CO₂ emissions:
The amount of carbon dioxide (CO₂) emitted during a given period of time. CO₂ emissions are typically measured in kilograms (kg) or tons (t).

In the circular economy, reducing energy consumption and CO₂ emissions is a key objective. By accurately recording and analyzing this energy consumption data, companies can take measures to save energy and reduce their carbon footprint, which contribute to more sustainable manufacturing.

4. Discussion

In this discussion, we evaluate our data model against key data requirements identified in the literature and demonstrate its applicability in a practical case study for a battery passport. The case study serves as a proof of concept for modeling a DPP based on the proposed approach. Further experimental verification is required to make the model more robust for practical applications. Our modeling approach effectively fulfills the data requirements identified by [25,26] for supporting a circular economy with the DPP.

We start with the data requirements identified in [25]. For manufacturing data, the Technical Data submodel template and Circularity Assessment submodel serve as a comprehensive source of technical data on product composition, material properties, and origin/destination of parts. These submodels standardize information crucial for product design and manufacturing processes, ensuring consistent and transparent communication across stakeholders. By including key details such as joining techniques and potential hazards, this approach not only fulfills manufacturing-related data requirements but also supports informed decision-making for both resource planning and safety across the product lifecycle. In terms of usage data, the Predictive Maintenance submodel template, specifically the Last Maintenance Relevant Events submodel element collection, documents critical information about part replacements, repairs, and damage—key factors highlighted by [25]. This submodel enables the detailed recording of maintenance history and component wear, helping operators track product health over time. By facilitating condition monitoring, fault diagnosis, and the prediction of remaining useful life, it allows stakeholders to choose the most appropriate R-strategy based on real-time data, contributing to prolonged product life and reduced waste. For end-of-life and lifecycle data, our model leverages the Return Options submodel and Circularity Assessment submodel, which collectively provide insights on available R-strategy services (such as recycling or refurbishing) and assess the product's circularity indicators, including repairability and reusability scores.

These indicators, aligned with standards like DIN EN 45554, support the goal of a circular economy by encouraging design choices that maximize reuse and recyclability. The Carbon Footprint submodel template and usage data on energy consumption and CO₂ emissions further address lifecycle data requirements by documenting environmental impacts and enabling users to monitor and reduce emissions.

Furthermore, our modeling approach meets the lifecycle-wide data requirements identified by [26]. For material data, the Technical Data submodel template in combination with the Hierarchical Structures submodel template plays a critical role by offering a standardized approach to documenting materials used in products, including details on type, specifications, and quantities. This detailed “bill of materials” supports recycling efforts by facilitating an understanding of a product’s material composition, which is essential for sustainable resource recovery. Environmental data requirements are addressed through the combination of the Technical Data, Carbon Footprint, and Usage Data submodels. These submodels enable lifecycle monitoring by tracking a product’s environmental impact, from material sourcing and production to its carbon footprint in use. The Carbon Footprint submodel template, in particular, documents emissions data and supports various calculation standards, allowing value chain partners to assess and optimize environmental impacts in alignment with sustainability initiatives. The Usage Data submodel complements this by recording CO₂ emissions and energy consumption during a product’s usage phase, capturing data that reflect real-world environmental performance. For manufacturing data, the Usage and Technical Data submodels together document production information, machine performance, and sensor data, fostering traceability and process optimization. Maintenance data requirements are met by the Predictive Maintenance submodel template, particularly through the Last Maintenance Relevant Events submodel element collection, which records maintenance history, repairs, and component wear. These data ensure that product health is consistently monitored and support timely interventions, enhancing product longevity. Finally, circularity and end-user data are documented within the Circularity Assessment, Return Options, and Usage Data submodels. The Circularity Assessment submodel provides key circularity indicators, such as the PCI, ECI and circularity design score, enabling stakeholders to track and improve circularity strategies over a product’s lifecycle. End-user data, including condition monitoring for operating parameters, help users make informed decisions about maintenance to prolong product usability. By supporting both high-level assessments and industry-specific standards, our modeling approach not only meets the core requirements identified by [25,26] but also sets the foundation for future scalability and adaptability to various product types and environmental regulations.

In the following, we want to focus our attention on applying our DPP modelling on a battery passport example because batteries are the first product category that will require a DPP. With the EU Battery Regulation 2023/1542 [40], from 2027, batteries (category: electric vehicle, light means of transport and industrial) above 2 kWh placed on the EU market will require a digital battery passport. The European Commission aims to promote sustainable and circular battery manufacturing through the introduction of this digital battery passport. As the first of several sector-specific DPPs planned for the future, the battery passport serves as a pilot implementation for the entire technical DPP system. In the regulation, the following information categories are mentioned:

- Carbon intensity of the manufacturing processes;
- Origin of the materials;
- Usage of renewable material;
- Composition of batteries;
- Raw materials and hazardous chemicals;
- Repair, repurposing, and dismantling operations and possibilities;

- Treatment, recycling, and recovery processes at the end of the lifetime.

These information categories are strictly required. However, usage data are beyond the required categories. Relevant usage data of the battery could be included in the battery passport, which would help in identifying the right R-strategy at the end of life. To model the information categories in the AAS, our model makes use of existing submodel templates to ensure interoperability and a common understanding. These cover some of the required categories and other useful data including dynamic data. However, not all aspects needed to infer the R-strategy are covered by submodel templates. As stated in Section 3, we created additional submodels that include information required to select and execute the most suitable R-strategy, in this case for batteries. This information is also explicitly stated to be required by the EU Battery Regulation, e.g., “recycling and recovery processes at the end of lifetime”.

As a baseline, we filled out the existing submodel templates for the battery:

- Digital nameplate;
- Hierarchical structures;
- Product carbon footprint;
- Technical data;
- Spare parts and consumables;
- Predictive maintenance.

These cover basic aspects like manufacturing metadata, composition, and the carbon emissions. We focused on the creation of a DPP for a single type of battery, since there were no DPPs for the components. In brown-field areas, components could already have a DPP based on these widely available submodel templates. The most trivial submodel template to fill out is the digital nameplate, since general information like the manufacturer address and serial numbers are entered. The other submodel templates require more details like the hierarchical structures, where the component layout is described. For the product carbon footprint, a standard should be selected to calculate the emissions and entered into the field “CalculationStandard”. This DPP will be the basis for the instances of the batteries. The PCF was estimated based on material and process reference values since no manufacturing process data were available. Such reference databases approximate the carbon emission. The predictive maintenance template is more relevant in other product categories like machines but information on refurbishment processes of certain battery cells could be described here. We left it empty indicating no maintenance on the battery instance was conducted.

Additionally, we filled out our submodels for the battery instances:

- Usage data
- Return options
- Circularity assessment
- Spare parts and consumables

For each battery instance, we include operational data like load cycles and operating times. These help in the evaluation process for the right R-strategy. A challenge might be to capture or maintain this dynamic data. In a lab scenario, it is trivial to keep track of the load cycles and charge states. In the case of car batteries, the battery passport could be updated with each car service maintenance by the service provider. The return options are also covered by a submodel and contain a list of viable return points. Here, we entered viable return options across our city where batteries can be returned, as well as the manufacturer, which carry out proper disposal or disassembly. Available spare parts and consumables are also listed in the respective submodel. If a battery needs a new enclosure, this submodel might provide the information needed to source the enclosure. This practice is not yet

common with manufacturers but could help customers exert their right to repair. Some of the data included in these submodels support the circularity assessment, for example, the calculation of circularity indicators like the product circularity indicator. This score evaluates the circularity of the battery in a quantitative way. However, the quantitative calculation of these metrics is not always clear, and standards should be adopted for the calculation [41]. We see this as the main benefit of our modeling approach since the data used for the indicators are also included and comparable across product categories. In the following section, we want to demonstrate the calculation of a repairability score based on our submodels.

To show the feasibility of our modeling approach, we are calculating a circularity design score for the battery to store inside the circularity assessment submodel. The previously mentioned DIN EN 45554 standard is our guideline for the calculation. The formula is stated in the following and includes a weighting for the parts and the criteria. W is the weighting of a priority part pp or criterion i assessed at priority part (j assessed at product level). S is the score of a criterion.

$$\text{Score} = \sum (W_{pp} \times \sum (W_i, pp \times S_i, pp)) + \sum W_j \times S_j$$

For simplicity, we are rating the battery as a whole without assessing the criteria of parts of the battery. We are also weighting all criteria equally. Our submodel circularity assessment includes a circularity design collection where all relevant properties are listed. Of course, when creating the model, it will be empty and as such we want to illustrate our approach when starting out to fill the model. Our battery will be a 12 V starter battery with a capacity of 190 Ah.

The first criterion is disassembly depth. In many cases, this depth can also be calculated with the submodel template hierarchical structures; however, this requires a complete product and part modeling. The formula for the depth with a part i is as follows:

$$S_{\text{depth},i} = 1 - \left(\frac{(D_i - 1)}{(D_{\text{ref}} - 1)} \right)$$

The bottom part includes the reference depth for the product group specified at a product-specific level. In our case, our battery is estimated to have the same disassembly depth as the reference and therefore the resulting disassembly depth is 0. The next criterion is a classification of the fastener system. Unfortunately, the disassembly of the starter battery requires cutting of the top part and therefore the fastener is hard to remove and not re-usable resulting in a score of C. The tools to repair the battery usually include basic tools, but experts might employ product-specific tools. Since this criterion evaluates feasibility, Class A (basic tools) takes precedence over Class B (product group specific tools). Regarding the working environment, it is not feasible to repair the battery inside the product use environment. A workshop environment (Class B) is required, and we even recommend a production-equivalent environment (Class C). Nonetheless, recycling centers with a workshop should be able to repair the battery in a safe manner and therefore Class B is chosen. For the skill level criterion, the disassembly has high safety risks like electric discharge and acids inside the battery. Only experts (Class C) should attempt the repair. Regarding the diagnostic support and interface, determining the state of the battery is challenging. In the best case, the voltage can be measured, and the surface can be examined for obvious damages or leaks. The performance data inside usage data could give hints to the last known throughput. However, a repair is usually attempted when the battery malfunctions and the exact source is not easily diagnosed through an interface resulting in Class E. Spare parts availability is also limited to the manufacturer and in most cases,

the starter battery is not repaired with spare parts from the manufacturer but recycled directly. Therefore, we would classify this as E as even the manufacturer will not acquire spare parts. Since the spare parts are not available to repairers, we will skip evaluating the spare part interface and the spare part availability duration. The next criterion is the types and availability of information. Unfortunately, there is no comprehensive information like circuit board schematics or step-by-step disassembly instructions available. In fact, there is no information available to repair, reuse or upgrade the battery (Class C). For the return options, basic return options like a local collection point are available (Class B) and the data management is classified with Class A since no data are stored. As previously mentioned, we will weigh all criteria equally and assign numerical values to the classes, i.e., A will be equal to 1 and B will be equal to 2:

$$\text{Score} = 0.1 \times (0 + 3 + 1 + 2 + 3 + 5 + 5 + 3 + 2 + 1) = 2.5$$

In total, we calculated and rounded up the repairability score to Class C. However, since all criteria were weighted equally, this is quite favorable because criteria like the data management and the required tools push the score towards Class B. This is why the score should be calculated with use-case-specific weightings to better infer the right R-strategies. This is also the main issue in many circularity indicators. The weighting can be manipulated to favor the assessment. In any case, all criteria are part of our modeling as properties, and the score can be quickly recalculated based on the values in the model. In the future, the operation to calculate the score could be part of the AAS model with individual weightings being provided as input parameters.

Regarding the feasibility of our approach for the future, most of our own proposed submodels regarding circularity should stay the same as they apply to a broad array of products and do not cover highly product-specific properties. A challenge might be the knowledge required to fill out all templates correctly. Currently, this is also a manual process requiring an AAS expert. However, recent advances in large language models allow the creation of modeling assistants, easing the creation process [42].

While this study provides a foundational data model for a DPP based on the AAS framework, certain research limitations must be acknowledged. First, the validation of the proposed model is primarily theoretical, necessitating further experimental verification to assess its real-world applicability. Second, while the model is designed for cross-industry use, the development of practical DPPs requires integrating sector-specific requirements for individual industries. Lastly, the availability and accessibility of data for modeling remain a significant challenge, particularly for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). Future research should explore methods for automated data extraction and develop intelligent services to support SMEs in obtaining and utilizing the necessary data efficiently. As the AAS standard continues to evolve, its role in supporting the circular economy can be further strengthened by incorporating new standards and calculation methodologies that reflect the unique sustainability requirements of different product categories. One series of such standards is ISO 59000 [43–46], a set of international standards aimed at providing unified guidelines for implementing circular economy practices across various industries. This series, which includes ISO 59004 [43], ISO 59010 [44], and ISO 59020 [45], introduces key concepts, principles, and frameworks for organizations transitioning to circular business models. However, many of the specific information requirements introduced by these standards were not available during the development of our DPP, as ISO 59040 [46] which is concerned with the product circularity data sheet is still under development as of November 2024. An alignment with international standards like this will further strengthen the applicability and interoperability of our DPP model.

5. Conclusions

This work focused on the research question: How can a digital product passport model based on the asset administration Shell be designed to support the circular economy while ensuring cross-industry applicability?

The circular economy is an ambitious yet promising concept for more sustainable manufacturing that addresses the environmental, as well as the economic and social dimension of sustainable manufacturing. The R-strategy framework presents a guiding principle for support of the circular economy. In this work, we decided to limit the scope on the R-strategies of remanufacturing, refurbishing, repair, and reuse because they are closely linked to production. The practical application of these R-strategies requires detailed information about the product from its entire lifecycle. This problem is addressed by the DPP.

In this study, we showed that the AAS framework presents a highly suitable foundation for modeling a DPP. By utilizing the AAS, DPPs benefit from standardized data structures and API capabilities that allow integration with existing product-specific data, avoiding redundancy and ensuring consistency across the product lifecycle. Key lifecycle stages, including material selection, manufacturing, usage, and end-of-life, are documented through AAS submodels that provide both static and dynamic data essential for circularity. Specifically, the established submodel templates for this DPP model included the Digital Nameplate, Technical Data, Predictive Maintenance, Hierarchical Structure, Carbon Footprint and Spare Parts submodel templates. A key contribution is that we complemented these submodel templates with the Circularity Assessment, Return Options and Usage Data submodels to close the informational gap regarding the effective utilization of R-strategies. This informational gap was derived from standards and the scientific literature and provided the data requirements for the submodels assuring applicability to various industries. In addition to modeling submodels that provide the necessary information for these R-strategies, we included KPIs that measure the circularity performance of products. This aids the design for circularity. Future research should focus on how the remaining R-strategies can be supported by the DPP.

In order to demonstrate that our DPP model is specific enough for practical application, we used it to model the battery passport for a specific battery and used it to calculate circularity performance indicators that help foster sustainable manufacturing and more sustainable design of products. Future research and development should focus on refining submodel templates specific to circularity metrics and usage data to broaden the applicability of DPPs across diverse industries and verifying these with comparative experiments. Moving forward, it will be crucial to align our proposed approach for a DPP model with emerging standards like the ISO 59000 series, particularly as additional documents like ISO 59040 are finalized.

Supplementary Materials: The following supporting information can be downloaded at: <https://github.com/Circular-TwAIn/CircularityAASModel/> (accessed on 16 June 2024). The file contains the entire data model.

Author Contributions: Conceptualization, M.K.; methodology, M.B. and M.K.; validation, F.V.; investigation, L.S., M.B. and M.K.; writing—original draft preparation, M.K.; writing—review and editing, F.V., L.S., M.B. and M.K.; funding acquisition, L.S. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research was partly funded by the H2020 Circular TwAIn project, which received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 101058585.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: See link for Supplementary Materials.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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